

Article Title: *User Adoption and Satisfaction in Government Digital Asset Systems: Evidence from SentinelTrack at a Philippine State University*

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Statement of Retraction

The *Journal of Critical Social Sciences and Review* is officially retracting the article titled "**User Adoption and Satisfaction in Government Digital Asset Systems: Evidence from SentinelTrack at a Philippine State University.**"

This retraction is being issued solely at the voluntary request of the author(s).

We clarify that this action is taken entirely based on the authors' decision to retract their work, and there are no violations of publishing ethics or misconduct involved.

The editorial team and the author(s) apologize for any inconvenience this may cause to our readers.

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